

Purpose and Intent: Two Governance Dimensions for Agent-Aware IAM

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Abstract

This paper extends the agent-aware IAM framework [1] by introducing purpose and intent as two formally distinct, complementary governance dimensions for agentic AI. Although both concepts are increasingly cited as answers to the governance challenge posed by autonomous agents, they are consistently used interchangeably and without formal grounding which has practical consequences: governance architectures enforcing runtime intent without managing purpose as a lifecycle attribute cannot prevent semantic privilege escalation, mission drift, and the reprompting problem.

We propose eight definitions that precisely distinguish *purpose*, a declared, lifecycle-governed attribute of an agent's digital identity, from *intent*, an inferred, session-scoped runtime signal. Two new governance constructs are introduced: the *purpose path*, a directed auditable record of purpose transitions over the agent's lifetime, and a *two-level governance architecture* connecting identity governance to runtime authorization through the *containment constraint* ($I(A,t) \subseteq Pe(A)$) and the *permission compatibility check* ($Pe(A) \subseteq PU(D)$). For multi-agent systems, a recursive containment constraint requires both a purpose chain requirement and an intent alignment requirement to hold simultaneously.

The framework maps directly to EU AI Act (Articles 9, 13, 14, 19) and GDPR (Article 5(1)(b)) obligations. An illustrative scenario demonstrates coherence across all governance constructs. Seven open problems are identified, with the granularity problem as the most immediately consequential for implementation.

Keywords

Agentic AI, agent-aware IAM, identity governance, purpose-based access control, intent-based access control, purpose lifecycle management, containment constraint, permission compatibility, purpose path, semantic privilege escalation, runtime authorization, multi-agent systems, recursive containment, EU AI Act, GDPR purpose limitation, non-human identity, intent confidence, identity fabric

1 Introduction

This paper extends the agent-aware IAM framework [1] by addressing a fundamental open question it left unresolved: if an agent is granted an access right, what does that access right ultimately refer to, not only which resources may be accessed, but also why the agent needs that access and with what scope of action.

The industry is rapidly converging on "purpose" and "intent" as the answers, but the terms are often used interchangeably and without formal grounding as reflected across vendor frameworks and industry analysis [3], [4], [5], [6], [27], [22], [27].

This conflation has practical consequences: governance architectures enforce runtime intent without managing purpose as a lifecycle attribute. The result is a class of named, observable failures, *semantic privilege escalation*, *mission drift*, the *reprompting problem*, that intent enforcement alone cannot prevent.

Regulatory obligations reinforce the urgency. The EU AI Act's obligations (Articles 9, 13, 14, 19) [2], and GDPR's purpose limitation principle (Article 5(1)(b)), [9], can only be meaningfully fulfilled if purpose and intent are treated as distinct, managed separately, and recorded separately.

We provide a conceptual and structural framework that formally distinguishes *purpose* (declared, lifecycle-governed, identity attribute) from *intent* (inferred, session-scoped, runtime signal), establishes the structural relationship between them through the *containment constraint* and the *permission compatibility* check, and derives governance implications for the agent-aware IAM framework.

Two new governance constructs are introduced: the *purpose path* (a directed, auditable record of purpose transitions over the agent's lifetime) and the *two-level governance architecture* (permission compatibility at governance time; containment constraint at runtime), expressible as $I(A,t) \subseteq P_c(A) \subseteq PU(D)$.

We identify and formally state the conflict case, which arises when agent intent and data-permitted-purpose are in tension, propose a partial resolution through the two-level architecture, and bound its limitations as the granularity problem. For multi-agent systems, we show that a recursive containment constraint is necessary: a sub-agent's runtime intent must satisfy both a purpose chain requirement and an intent alignment requirement simultaneously.

The paper addresses agentic AI as autonomous, goal-directed, indeterministic systems. It is a conceptual and structural paper; formal models and implementation architectures are left for future work. Literature cutoff: April 30, 2026.

2 Background and Related Work

The emergence of agentic AI systems exposes fundamental limitations in traditional Identity and Access Management (IAM). Autonomous agents do not simply execute predefined workflows; they reason, plan, and adapt at runtime. Authorization decisions must therefore address not only *who* accesses *what*, but also *why* an action is taken and whether it remains within an authorized scope. Two concepts - **purpose** and **intent** - are increasingly referenced in both research and industry to answer these questions, but they appear in separate academic traditions and are conflated in industry practice. This section reviews how each is treated in prior work, and identifies the structural gap that Sections 3 and 4 address.

2.1 Purpose in Research

The academic treatment of **Purpose** in access control provides a rigorous and directly relevant foundation. Purpose-Based Access Control (PBAC) established the distinction between *intended purpose* - the reason a data element was collected - and *access purpose* - the reason it is being requested at runtime - and formalized compatibility checks between the two purpose variants [7], [8]. Subsequent work extended this into conflict analysis, privacy-aware role models, and GDPR alignment [10], [11], [12]. The intended-purpose versus access-purpose distinction maps directly onto the permission compatibility check we introduce in section 3.5.

The PBAC tradition was designed for a context in which purpose is human-declared, relatively stable, and attached to data or roles, and it performs well in that context. What it was not designed for is the lifecycle of an autonomous agent: re-tasking, delegation, drift, and the question of whether an agent's authorized mandate remains appropriate as its operational context evolves. These are not failures of the research so much as boundaries of its original scope. AI systems research, for its part, treats purpose as an engineering assumption embedded in system prompts or reward functions which is practical for deployment but not structured for governance. The result is that purpose appears either as formally precise but static, or as operationally dynamic but ungoverned. Bridging that gap is the motivation for the purpose path construct and its lifecycle governance implications, introduced in Sections 3.1 and 4.2.

A terminological note: PBAC is used inconsistently in the literature, denoting both *Purpose-Based* and *Policy-Based* Access Control; the latter a generalization of RBAC/ABAC common in vendor documentation. This paper uses PBAC exclusively in the academic, purpose-based sense.

2.2 Intent in Research

Runtime security research has made substantive progress on intent as a governance signal. Work on prompt injection, confused-deputy attacks, and goal hijacking has established intent misalignment as a meaningful failure category [13], and recent approaches to runtime intent inference and continuous authorization represent genuine advances in detecting what an agent is attempting moment to moment [14], [15]. These advances directly inform the intent inference approaches we present in Section 4.3.

The scope of runtime security research is, by design, session-bound: intent is inferred at the start of an interaction, evaluated against immediate context, and not persisted beyond the session. This is appropriate for its intention, detecting in-session misalignment, but it means that questions spanning sessions are outside its frame. Whether an agent's operational scope has shifted in ways that were never authorized, whether drift has accumulated across interactions, whether a re-tasking was governed or invisible, none of these are questions the current runtime intent literature is positioned to answer. They require a connection between the session-level signal and the lifecycle-level authorization that the existing work does not establish.

An earlier thread is also worth noting: Almeahmadi [16] proposed dynamically scoring human user intent from physiological signals to gate access decisions, an early formal treatment of intent as something measured rather than declared. LLM-assisted policy work has more recently proposed natural language intent specifications with automated compliance checking [17]. Neither addresses agentic systems directly, but both point in the direction we develop: intent as a governed attribute, not only a behavioral signal. Note that the acronym IBAC carries multiple unrelated meanings in the literature, including the traditional Identity-Based Access Control model, and we avoid it for the same reason we define PBAC precisely.

The containment constraint we explain in Section 3.3 provides the formal connection between session-level intent and lifecycle-level purpose. The misalignment taxonomy in Section 4.4 maps the failure modes that arise when that connection is absent or violated.

2.3 Purpose and Intent in Adjacent Fields

Traditional authorization models like RBAC, ABAC, policy-based access control, were not designed to govern autonomous behavior, and it shows. They answer the question of *who* can do *what* under specified conditions competently, but they assume that requests are intrinsically legitimate and that the identity making them is stable. Neither assumption holds for agentic AI. An agent operating under a manipulated prompt, a re-tasked configuration, or an accumulated context that has drifted from its original mandate will pass every traditional access check while doing precisely what it should not be doing. The permission compatibility check we explain in Section 3 is the mechanism that fills the data-side gap these models leave open.

Threat-modeling frameworks for agentic AI, notably the OWASP multi-agent threat modeling guide [19], have identified the surface-level symptoms: cascading tool misuse, unauthorized delegation, goal hijacking. These are useful catalogs of what can go wrong. What they do not provide is a governance model for why it goes wrong at the authorization level, which failures are provisioning errors, which are runtime drift, which are adversarial manipulation, and what the appropriate response is in each case. The misalignment taxonomy in Section 4.4 makes those distinctions explicit and maps each type to the governance layer responsible for it.

The regulatory picture sharpens the urgency. The EU AI Act [2] leans heavily on *intended purpose* to define risk classification, transparency obligations, human oversight, and audit

requirements (Articles 9, 13, 14, 19), yet says nothing about runtime intent and provides no mechanism to verify that an agent's evolving behavior remains aligned with the purpose declared at deployment. GDPR's purpose limitation principle (Article 5(1)(b)) [9] creates a parallel obligation on the data side. Both frameworks assume that someone, somewhere, is maintaining the connection between declared purpose and actual behavior, but they do not specify how. That responsibility falls to IAM and governance layers, and it is currently unmet. The purpose path we explain in Section 3.1, is the audit artefact that satisfies the EU AI Act's logging and lifecycle risk requirements; the permission compatibility check addresses GDPR's data-side obligation. In Section 4.4, we trace both these connections in detail.

2.4 The Current Industry Landscape and Its Gap

The industry has moved fast. Since 2025, a recognizable market category has emerged, variously called Agentic Access Management (AAM) or Agentic Identity Access Platforms [6] with real capabilities: explicit agent identities, just-in-time credentials, ownership models, and runtime intent enforcement. These are meaningful advances over the long-lived service account model that preceded them, and they represent the field's best current answer to the governance problem.

The most advanced platforms have arrived at a formulation that is close to ours but stops short of it. Leading vendors now define agent integrity as operating within the boundaries of intended purpose and expected behavior, with intent alignment as the first governance pillar. The framing that has consolidated across analyst and vendor discourse positions the shift as: identity answers *who*, intent answers *why*. The failure mode which this framing targets, has a precise name: *semantic privilege escalation*, where an agent operates within valid technical permissions while exceeding the semantic scope of its assigned task; every access check passes, but governance has failed. That framing is exactly right, and the containment constraint in Section 3.3 is its formal expression. The ACME scenario explained in chapter 6 illustrates it concretely.

What no current platform provides is a governance model for purpose itself. Purpose in every current implementation is either static metadata set at provisioning time or a task-level time-scope for credential validity. There is no model for how purpose changes legitimately, how change is authorized and audited, how it propagates through delegation chains, or how unintended drift is detected and governed. The *reprompting problem*, where a user redirects an agent beyond its original configuration, effectively shifting its operative mandate without triggering any governance event, is a direct and well-documented consequence of this absence, and one we illustrate in Section 6.

Standards bodies are catching up but are not yet there. NIST NCCoE [20] names intent logging as a formal governance requirement for the first time at the standards level which is a significant step, while still framing the problem in terms of runtime evidence rather than lifecycle purpose governance. Gartner's introduction of the Agent Development Life Cycle as a named governance practice [21] and Forrester's characterization of intent as the defining feature distinguishing agentic AI from all prior software deployments [22] confirm that the conceptual need is widely recognized. A recent CSA survey puts the implementation gap in

empirical terms: nearly half of organizations are governing agents by extending human IAM models, and only 18% express confidence that their current approach is adequate [23].

The gap this paper addresses is precise: the academic PBAC tradition provides formal purpose semantics but treats purpose as static and data-attached; the emerging AAM category enforces intent at session speed but leaves purpose as an ungoverned provisioning label. Neither connects the two through a formal containment relationship, and neither treats purpose as a dynamic, lifecycle-governed identity attribute with traceable transitions, delegation semantics, and regulatory mapping. The definitions in chapter 3, governance implications in chapter 4, open questions in chapter 5, and the illustrative scenario in chapter 6 together close that gap.

3 Definitions

In this chapter, we propose definitions for *purpose* and *intent* in the context of agentic AI and agent-aware IAM. These definitions make the required governance controls visible and provide the conceptual foundation for the implications discussed in Chapter 4.

For clarification, we will provide summaries of the definitions of our previous paper [1], for details on these definitions, we refer to this paper.

A **Digital Identity** represents an entity in the context of IAM and includes all information necessary for IAM-related activities around this entity. The entity can be a human being or non-human entities. A Digital Identity includes several attributes for the entity, e.g., unique identifier, type, status, account(s), credentials, organizational attributes (cost center, manager, owner).

An **Identity Fabric** is a cohesive and comprehensive architectural framework that consolidates IAM components into an integrated system, making it easier to combine services and respond flexibly to changing IAM needs, emerging technologies, and shifting business requirements.

An **AI agent** refers to a *single* autonomous AI entity that can perceive its environment, make decisions, and take actions to achieve goals. AI Agents can range from a simple entity like a chatbot to complex entities, e.g., an AI that plans multi-step tasks.

Agentic AI describes AI systems that show autonomous, goal-directed behavior without constant human guidance; they may deploy a single AI agent or coordinate multiple AI agents to achieve their objectives. Unlike traditional AI that simply reacts to prompts, agentic AI can plan, make decisions, and use tools independently. It breaks down complex goals into logical steps and adapts its approach based on new information or changing conditions.

In chapter 6, we will illustrate the following definitions and requirements with the ACME HR Orchestration Agent scenario to make these more tangible for the reader.

3.1 Purpose: A Lifecycle Attribute of An Agentic AI Agent

Definition 1 (Purpose)

***Purpose** is the declared, policy-level reason for which an agent has been provisioned and authorized to act. It is an attribute of the agent's Digital Identity, registered at provisioning time, and subject to governed change over the agent's lifecycle.*

This definition leads to specific properties of purpose:

- Purpose is *prospective*: it authorizes a class of actions before they occur.
- Purpose is *declared*, not inferred, by a human authority, as part of the identity governance process.
- Purpose can change, on a legitimate basis like re-tasking, delegation narrowing.
- Purpose might change illegitimately through e.g., drift, prompting, manipulation.

In some cases, we will distinguish between the declared purpose and the effective purpose:

Definition 2 (Declared Purpose, Effective Purpose)

*The **declared purpose** is the purpose of an agent registered at initial provisioning.*

*The **effective purpose** is the purpose of an agent which is currently authorized and may have been updated through a governed change event.*

Therefore, at provisioning time, effective purpose is the declared purpose. Effective purpose diverges from declared purpose after a governed change event.

In comparison to traditional IAM, purpose can be seen as analogous to a role or job function, which is stable but not immutable. Just as a role change is a lifecycle event requiring governance, a purpose change is a lifecycle event requiring governance too.

Definition 3 (Purpose Path)

*Therefore, we define the **Purpose Path** which is a directed, auditable record of purpose transitions over the agent's lifetime. Each node is a purpose state; each edge is a transition event with metadata, including the preceding and resulting purpose states, the authorizing party, the trigger event, the trust level required, and the timestamp.*

3.2 Intent: A Session-Scoped Attribute of An Agentic AI Agent

Definition 4 (Intent)

***Intent** is the inferred, runtime expression of what an agent is attempting to accomplish within a specific execution context (session/task). It is the operational instantiation of the effective purpose at a point in time.*

This definition leads to specific properties of intent:

- Intent is *present-tense*: it characterizes what the agent is doing *now*, not what it is generally authorized to do.
- Intent is *inferred*, not declared, from prompts, task descriptions, tool call sequences, or behavioral patterns.
- Intent is *ephemeral*, scoped to a session or sub-task, not persisted as an identity attribute.

In traditional IAM terms, intent operates at the runtime authorization layer rather than the identity governance layer.

We can summarize the provided definitions on purpose and intent in the following table.

Dimension	Purpose	Intent
Definition	Declared, policy-level reason for which an agent is provisioned and authorized to act	Inferred, runtime expression of what the agent is attempting to accomplish in a given session
Nature	Declared	Inferred
Scope	Lifecycle, persists across sessions	Session, ephemeral, not persisted as identity attribute
Governance layer	Identity governance	Runtime authorization
Established by	Human authority, at provisioning or governed change event	Governance system, e.g., from prompt analysis, behavioral inference, or signed intent (see section 4.3)
Can change?	Yes, through governed lifecycle events recorded on the purpose path	Yes, continuously within a session, resets between sessions
Relationship	Provides the boundary	What the agent pursues within that boundary at any given moment
Checked against	Data permitted-use labels (Permission Compatibility, section 3.5)	Effective purpose (Containment Constraint, section 3.3)

Table 1: Overview of Purpose and Intent and their properties

3.3 The Structural Relationship Between Purpose and Intent: The Containment Constraint

Definition 5 (Containment Constraint)

*The differentiation between purpose and intent brings us to an important requirement for agents, the **containment constraint**:*

A well-governed agent's runtime intent falls within the scope of its effective purpose.

Therefore, purpose provides the *boundary* for intent, and intent is *what the agent pursues within that boundary at any given moment*.

If the containment constraint is not fulfilled, this implicates that governance has failed. Examples can be that intent exceeds purpose, e.g., though mission drift, prompt injection; or that purpose was never adequate to begin with, which would be a provisioning failure.

The containment constraint is the governance mechanism which connects the two dimensions through checking at runtime if the current intent falls within the effective purpose. This creates the link between the identity governance layer and the runtime authorization layer.

Traditional IAM answers the question of “who” is accessing “what”, the containment constraint answers “why” does “who” access “what”.

3.4 Discussion on Intent and Purpose as Attribute of Identity or Data

As shown in the chapter on background and related work, Purpose-Based Access Control tradition places "purpose" on data, so that data carries labels specifying the permitted purposes for which it may be accessed.

In agent-aware IAM, purpose and intent are placed on the agent, and the agent's current intent is inferred and checked against its authorized purpose.

Both placements are valid, and they address different governance questions:

- Is the agent acting within its authorized scope?
- Is this data being accessed for a permitted reason?

These distinctions matter and open a question which is not addressed yet neither in the Purpose-Based Access Control literature nor in Agent-Aware IAM publications:

- What happens when agent intent and data-permitted purpose conflict?

Definition 6 (Conflict Case)

*If the agent intent and data-permitted purpose conflict, we will define this situation as the **conflict case**.*

The conflict case is important to be handled especially in the context of regulations like GDPR and the EU AI Act.

3.5 The Relationship Between Purpose and Data: The Permission Compatibility

Definition 7 (Permission Compatibility, Permission Compatibility Check)

*The different assignment of the purpose as attribute to the identity in IAM and as attribute of data in privacy brings us to another requirement, the **permission compatibility**:*

A well-governed agent's effective purpose falls within the set of purposes for which the data it accesses is permitted to be used.

*The **permission compatibility check** is a governance verification which is performed at provisioning time and at each purpose change event and that confirms whether the agent's effective purpose is compatible with the permitted-use labels of the data resources it is authorized to access.*

3.6 The Two-Layer Governance Architecture

While the containment constraint checks whether runtime intent falls within effective purpose (a runtime check), the permission compatibility check verifies whether effective purpose is compatible with the data being accessed (a governance-time check).

Together they form a two-level governance architecture shown in picture 1:

- Data-permitted labels govern declared purpose, and any subsequent updates to effective purpose, through the permission compatibility check at provisioning and change time.
- Effective purpose then governs runtime intent through the containment constraint.

Figure 1: Two-Level Governance Architecture: Permission Compatibility Check and Containment Constraint

3.7 Notation

We use the following notation to compactly express the relationships described in the previous sections; a full formal treatment is left for future work.

Containment constraint

If $P_e(A)$ is the effective purpose of agent A , and $I(A,t)$ is the intent of agent A at a time t , then the containment constraint can be written as

$$I(A,t) \subseteq P_e(A) \quad (1)$$

Permission compatibility:

If $P_e(A)$ is the effective purpose of agent A , and $PU(D)$ denotes the permitted-use labels of data resource D , then the permission compatibility can be written as

$$P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D) \quad (2)$$

The two-level governance architecture

When both constraints are satisfied, the two-level governance architecture can be expressed as a transitive relationship in that notation as

$$I(A,t) \subseteq P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D) \quad (3)$$

This expresses the governance ideal: an agent's runtime intent falls within its effective purpose, which in turn falls within the purposes for which the data it accesses is permitted to be used.

In section 4.6, we will discuss the limitations of the two-level governance architecture and in which cases it will produce a formally valid conclusion that is a substantively wrong.

4 Implications for Agentic AI Governance

In this chapter, we will discuss which implications the definitions of purpose and intent and the described requirements have for the Agent-Aware IAM Framework presented in [1].

In chapter 6, we will walk through the described implications with the ACME/HROA scenario to show that the framework is coherent.

4.1 Purpose as an Identity Lifecycle Attribute: Extending the Agent-Aware IAM Framework

In the previous section, we have defined purpose as attribute of an agent's identity. This means, purpose has to be added as a formal attribute to the Digital Identity of the agent when setting up the agent, similar to other attributes like ownership and assigned roles.

Similar to the classical identity governance processes like joiner, mover, leaver, the purpose can change with specific lifecycle events:

- The initial provisioning as declaration of the purpose for that agent;
- A re-tasking of the agent through a governed purpose change as in a role change which leads to an updated effective purpose;
- Narrowing the purpose of an agent through delegation which leads to an updated effective purpose too;
- And finally, the expiry of the agent's purpose through a decommissioning process.

As in classical identity governance, all the events and changes have to be logged in the purpose path which will provide the lifecycle-level audit architecture for the purpose attribute.

The purpose path is the audit mechanism which will show compliance (or non-compliance) to regulatory requirements. We will discuss that in more detail in section 4.2.

4.2 Why Purpose Must Be Treated as a Changeable Lifecycle Attribute

In the last months, we had several discussions with clients and practitioners on the question if purpose is an immutable or a changeable attribute of the agent. This distinction touches also a question in the NIST concept paper [20], which asks if agent identities should be ephemeral (task-specific) or fixed.

If purpose would be immutable, then purpose changes would be handled through decommissioning and re-provisioning like traditional applications. For the sake of simplicity, we will call this approach a *static governance model*.

A static governance model that can only represent two states, provisioned and decommissioned, is insufficient for the operational realities of autonomous agents and agentic AI deployed at enterprise scale.

We will discuss this statement in more detail in this section, using just one small example to illustrate the situation.

Example: An enterprise deploys a research agent with the declared purpose of summarizing industry reports. The business decides that the agent should also draft executive briefings from those summaries.

In the static governance model, a new agent would have to be created and deployed. In practice, organizations would simply reconfigure the existing agent through changing its system prompts, expand its tool access, update its instructions, and continue using it. The agent's identity with its credentials, its API keys, its registered service account, would persist. Only its declared purpose has changed.

This approach happens constantly in real deployments. The question is not if purpose change should happen, the question is if it happens governed or ungoverned.

Therefore, the static governance model does not prevent purpose change as it has no governance framework for it. This means, in the static governance model, purpose change happens invisibly.

Even if the static governance model would work for intentional purpose changes, the model does not address unintended purpose drift through accumulated context, tool chain effects, or prompt injection which is the more dangerous case.

In our lifecycle governance model, it is acknowledged that purpose can change, and the framework provides governance capabilities for when it does. The purpose path as defined in section 3.1 is then the artefact which provides the governance trail for purpose changes.

4.3 Measuring Intent at Runtime

As in Definition 4 in section 3.2 , we have defined intent I as $I(A,t)$ which is the operational instantiation of effective purpose of an agent A at a point in time t .

To show that the intent $I(A,t)$ fulfils the containment constraint, it must be checked against the effective purpose of an agent. This leads directly to the question on how intent can be measured at runtime.

In the current research and industry practice, three main approaches can be identified. Each of them has different trust properties and operating characteristics. The choice of a specific approach determines what the containment constraint can reliably enforce. In this section, we will discuss these three approaches.

4.3.1 Prompt and Task Analysis

*The **prompt and task analysis** approach infers intent from the natural language instruction (prompt) that initiated the agent's current session. The governing system parses the prompt and derives a structured representation of what the agent appears to be attempting.*

This approach is fast and human-readable, but prone to errors: prompts can be vague, misleading, or manipulated through prompt injection. A useful measure of this susceptibility to error is **prompt fidelity**, which Sinha defines as the ratio of constraints in a prompt that are verified by tool calls versus those that are inferred by the agent's internal reasoning [24]. A low prompt fidelity means that inferred intent is weakly based on what was actually requested.

4.3.2 Behavioral Inference

*The **behavioral inference** approach observes what the agent actually does rather than what it claims to be doing, deriving intent from the sequence of tool calls, data accesses, and intermediate reasoning steps during execution.*

This approach has been described as governance mechanism by Zenity [25] and in Microsoft's Agent Governance Toolkit [26].

This approach is more robust and sensitive to drift, as an agent whose behavior diverges from the baseline established for its effective purpose will produce a detectable signal even if its stated intent appears unchanged. The limitation is latency and baseline dependency: detection is retrospective rather than preventive, and newly provisioned agents have no established baseline.

4.3.3 Signed Intent

*The **signed intent** approach requires the agent to explicitly declare its intent in a structured, cryptographically attested form before executing a discrete action. The declaration is signed with a key tied to the agent's identity, producing an attributable, non-repudiable record.*

The approach has been formally described by the CSA as broader governance principle: Signed intent guarantees attribution: who made the request, when, what the payload was, and why the action was believed to be legitimate [27].

The approach is mainly implemented in the financial domain: Mastercard Verifiable Intent [28] links a consumer's identity, original instructions, and transaction outcome into a single tamper-resistant record. Google's Agent Payments Protocol [29] formalizes this through cryptographically signed *Mandates* as verifiable proof of user instructions.

This described approach does not guarantee that the claimed intent is itself within the agent's effective purpose. The containment constraint must still be evaluated against the signed claim.

4.3.4 Comparison of the Three Approaches

The three approaches are complementary ways that address different governance challenges at different timescales:

- Prompt analysis establishes an initial intent representation at session start;
- Behavioral inference monitors continuously throughout execution;
- Signed Intent produces attributable records at discrete high-stakes action points.

Because the weaknesses of each approach are compensated by the strengths of the others, the three approaches are complementary and best deployed together.

4.3.5 Intent Confidence as a Cross-Cutting Dimension

We will introduce the concept of **Intent Confidence** as a fourth dimension which cuts across the three approaches described above and which will define how a governance system decides which actions to take based on the results of the measured intent.

Definition 8 (Intent Confidence)

***Intent Confidence** is the degree of certainty with which a governance system can establish that an agent's inferred runtime intent accurately represents what the agent is actually attempting to accomplish.*

It is determined by the inference approach used, the quality and consistency of available signals, and the absence of indicators of manipulation or drift.

Intent confidence governs the response to the containment check:

- high confidence permits automatic enforcement;
- low confidence triggers a restricted permission set or escalation to human oversight.

This can be summarized as such:

Intent confidence is the assessed reliability of an inferred intent claim, the basis on which a governance system determines whether to enforce the containment constraint automatically or to escalate.

Banerjee has introduced the Mean Time to Understand (MTU) metric in his CSA blog [30]: MTU measures how quickly a governance system can build a usable semantic model of agent intent sufficient to make a secure authorization decision.

This means that MTU provides the operational constraint on intent confidence: a governance system that cannot comprehend agent intent quickly enough will systematically produce low-confidence inferences, regardless of which approach it uses.

The formal treatment of how these three approaches interact, and how intent confidence should be operationalized as a governance variable, is left as a direction for future work (see 5.3).

4.4 Validating Intent Against Purpose: The Containment Check in Practice

The containment check operationalizes the framework introduced in the preceding sections: it verifies whether current intent falls within effective purpose.

Violations of the containment constraint and the misalignment of purpose and intent can have various reasons with distinct causes and governance responses. The following table provides an overview of several reasons for misalignments.

Misalignment type	Cause	Governance layer	Response
Legitimate re-tasking	Authorized business decision	Identity governance	Purpose path update
Delegated narrowing	Multi-agent orchestration	Identity governance	Delegation chain governance
Emergent drift	Context loss, tool chain effects	Runtime	Continuous monitoring, intent confidence check
Adversarial manipulation	Prompt injection	Runtime	Detection, revocation, incident log

Table 2: Types of Misalignments between purpose and intent

4.4.1 The Recursive Containment Constraint in Multi-Agent Systems

In multi-agent systems, e.g., from delegated narrowing, the containment constraint is in fact a set of two requirements for sub-agents which must fulfil the **recursive containment constraint**:

In multi-agent systems, a sub-agent's runtime intent must satisfy two requirements simultaneously:

- *it must fall within the sub-agent's own effective purpose, which must itself be a subset of the parent agent's effective purpose (the **purpose chain requirement**);*
- *and it must be consistent with the parent agent's runtime intent at the same moment (the **intent alignment requirement**).*

In our notation, it can be written for the parent agent pA and the sub-agent sA as follows:

$$I(sA, t) \subseteq P_e(sA) \subseteq P_e(pA) \quad \text{and} \quad I(sA, t) \subseteq I(pA, t). \quad (4)$$

Therefore, purpose provides the structural governance constraint through the hierarchy; intent alignment provides the dynamic governance constraint at runtime. Both are necessary; neither is sufficient alone.

This two-part recursive containment constraint is what distinguishes multi-agent governance from single-agent governance; this topic is currently unaddressed in the literature (see 5.5).

We will apply this recursive containment check to sub-agents in our scenario in chapter 6.

4.4.2 Purpose Hierarchies and Temporal Drift

In **purpose hierarchies**, the main question is if a purpose P also authorizes sub-purposes. Here the containment check can support the differentiation between legitimate sub-scope, which means intent is a valid instantiation of purpose, and illegitimate drift which means intent has exceeded purpose.

One open point is **temporal drift**, which means that intent is within scope at session initiation, but may drift out of scope mid-session. Here the containment constraint will not support clarification. (see 5.4).

4.4.3 Regulatory Note

The misalignment types identified above map directly to specific EU AI Act obligations:

- EU AI Act Article 14 (human oversight) is undermined by emergent drift;
- EU AI Act Article 15 (robustness) is violated by adversarial manipulation;
- EU AI Act Article 19 (logs) must capture which type of misalignment occurred.

The containment check connects directly to EU AI Act Article 14 (human oversight): humans set the purpose boundary; the containment check is the mechanism by which that boundary is enforced at machine speed.

4.5 The Purpose Path as Regulatory Compliance Mechanism

As defined in section 3.1, the purpose path is the directed, auditable record of purpose transitions over the agent's lifetime.

This makes the purpose path a governance artefact which shows compliance or non-compliance to requirements in the EU AI Act and the GDPR through a single audit artefact:

- The purpose path is the data structure that enables compliance with EU AI Act Article 19 (automatic log generation) and Article 9 (lifecycle risk management) in a meaningful way, the EU AI Act purpose requirements apply to the system dimension.
- The GDPR purpose limitation (Article 5(1)(b)) applies to the data dimension.

4.6 The Limitations of the Two-Level Governance Architecture

The two-level governance architecture described in section 3.6 can be expressed in that notation: $I(A,t) \subseteq P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D)$

There are three cases to look into:

Case 1: The containment constraint check fails at runtime: $I(A,t) \not\subseteq P_e(A)$

This means, the agent's runtime intent exceeds the effective purpose, so the chain breaks as designed and the two-level governance architecture has worked correctly by detecting that failure.

Case 2: The permission compatibility check fails at governance time: $P_e(A) \not\subseteq PU(D)$

This means that the agent's effective purpose is not compatible with the permitted-use labels of the data, therefore the chain breaks as designed before runtime. Again, the two-level governance architecture has worked correctly by detecting that failure.

Case 3: The granularity problem

This is the case where both steps appear to hold individually, but the transitivity produces a wrong result.

We will illustrate that case with a small example to make it better understandable, when and why it can happen.

***Example:** An agent has an effective purpose "Customer Account Management". The data's permitted-use labels include "Account Management". So effective purpose is within permitted use:*

$P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D)$

The agent's runtime intent is "Export all account records to an external analytics platform". This is a plausible sub-scope of "Customer Account Management", so intent is contained within effective purpose:

$$I(A,t) \subseteq P_e(A)$$

Therefore, by transitivity would the export action be compatible with the data's permitted-use label: $I(A,t) \subseteq PU(D)$

But the data was collected for account management in the sense of supporting individual customer interactions, not for bulk export to analytics platforms. The permitted-use label *account management* was never intended to cover that use of data. The transitivity has led to a formally valid conclusion that is factually incorrect.

The reason for that had been a failure of the granularity at which purpose and permitted-use labels are defined.

Therefore, the transitivity chain depends on the condition that purpose and permitted-use labels are defined at sufficient granularity to exclude actions that are technically within scope but substantively inappropriate. When definitions are too coarse, the chain may hold formally while providing a weaker governance guarantee than needed.

"This is the *granularity problem*. Although the PBAC literature has addressed related granularity challenges for data-side purpose labels [7], [8], extending equivalent precision to the agent-purpose dimension remains unresolved. We discuss this as a bounded open question in section 5.6.

5 Open Questions and Possible Research

This paper establishes purpose and intent as distinct but complementary governance dimensions within agent aware IAM. Several important questions remain open. These questions arise directly from the framework introduced here and point toward areas where further formalization, systems research, and standards work are required.

5.1 Formalizing Purpose-Intent Containment

The containment constraint is introduced conceptually; its formalization remains an open problem. Determining whether a specific runtime intent falls within a declared purpose requires machine-interpretable representations of both constructs and a well-defined notion of scope. Open questions include how purpose hierarchies should be modeled, how sub-purposes inherit constraints, and how to distinguish legitimate specialization from drift. The PBAC literature addresses compatibility for data access [8], [11], but extending these models to autonomous agents with evolving intent remains largely unexplored.

***Example:** An agent provisioned for "customer support" receives a task to resolve a billing dispute. Whether this falls within its authorized scope, or represents an expansion into financial processing, cannot currently be determined computationally without a formal containment model.*

5.2 Representing Purpose as an Identity Attribute

This paper treats purpose as a lifecycle attribute of an agent's digital identity, analogous to but distinct from roles in human IAM. How purpose should be represented technically remains open. Possible approaches include structured attributes, policy references, graph-based representations, or verifiable claims. Further research is needed to assess which representations best support identity governance operations such as approval workflows, delegation, auditability, and cross-domain trust in identity fabric architectures [31], [32].

***Example:** When a sub-agent is delegated a narrowed purpose, that purpose must be representable in a form evaluable by the runtime authorization layer, verifiable by the parent agent, and auditable by a compliance team. No current identity standard satisfies all three requirements simultaneously.*

5.3 Intent Inference and Confidence

Multiple inference strategies exist: prompt analysis, behavioral modeling, and signed intent, each with different tradeoffs between robustness, latency, and explainability [14], [15]. An open question is how intent confidence should be assessed and incorporated into authorization decisions, and how inferred intent can be explained to human overseers in a way that supports accountability and regulatory audit. The MTU metric [30] frames the operational constraint usefully, but a complete treatment of how confidence should be operationalized as a governance variable remains to be developed.

***Example:** An agent executing a multi-step pipeline produces dozens of tool calls within seconds. Prompt analysis established an initial intent at session start, but behavioral inference has no baseline yet for this agent. The governance system must make authorization decisions under low-confidence inferred intent with no clear policy for when to restrict or escalate.*

5.4 Governing Purpose Change and Drift

The framework explicitly allows purpose to change through governed lifecycle events, but detecting and classifying purpose change remains challenging. Legitimate re-tasking, delegated narrowing, unintentional drift, and adversarial manipulation may appear similar at runtime but require different governance responses. Developing mechanisms to detect gradual drift, caused by prompt evolution, context accumulation, or tool-chain effects, is an important area for future research.

Example: An agent's system prompt is updated incrementally over several weeks, each change minor and individually reasonable. In aggregate, the agent's effective purpose has shifted significantly, but no single update triggered a governance review. The purpose path records each declared state; detecting that the cumulative drift constitutes an ungoverned purpose change requires mechanisms the framework does not yet specify.

5.5 Multi-Agent Delegation and Inheritance

The recursive containment constraint in Section 4.4.1 establishes the structural requirement for sub-agents. What remains open is how purpose authority propagates across delegation chains of arbitrary depth, how narrowing is enforced at each step, and how revocation at a parent level reaches active sub-agents. Formal models for purpose inheritance, narrowing, and revocation in multi-agent environments are a necessary next step [18].

Example: If a parent agent's purpose is narrowed by a human override mid-execution, there is currently no mechanism to propagate that change in real time to a sub-agent already operating under the original, broader scope.

5.6 The Granularity Problem

As identified in Section 4.6, when purpose statements and permitted-use labels are defined at insufficient granularity, the transitivity chain $I(A,t) \subseteq Pe(A) \subseteq PU(D)$ can hold formally while producing a substantively incorrect governance conclusion.

This problem is not entirely new: Bertino's foundational PBAC work on purpose hierarchies [7], [8] was partly motivated by the need to navigate granularity in data-side purpose labels, establishing that general purposes do not automatically permit specific sub-purposes.

However, that work addresses the data dimension in relatively static database contexts; extending equivalent precision to the agent-purpose dimension, where purposes are dynamic, delegated, and subject to drift, remains an open problem. Resolving this requires work on purpose ontologies, permitted-use label standards, and minimum specificity requirements. It is the most immediately consequential open question for practitioners implementing the framework, and likely requires domain-specific solutions rather than a general answer.

Example: An agent with purpose "account management" is granted access to data labelled "account management use." Both checks pass formally, but the data was scoped to individual customer interactions, not the bulk export the agent performs. The governance architecture produced a valid result on inputs that were too coarsely defined.

5.7 Attribution and Root-Cause Analysis of Agent Actions

When agent behavior results in a security incident, enterprises must reconstruct not only who acted and what action occurred, but why and if it fell within the agent's authorized mandate. Unlike incidents involving human users, agent-driven failures may result from intent drift, mis-delegation, prompt manipulation, or emergent behavior rather than explicit misuse. Current IAM and security tooling provides limited visibility into how an action related to the agent's intent or purpose at the time of execution [13]. Developing audit-grade mechanisms that correlate agent actions with inferred intent and effective purpose is a direct dependency on open questions 1, 2, and 3. The purpose path and session-level intent logs introduced in this paper are the prerequisite data structures for this capability: their existence is necessary but not sufficient.

Example: A post-incident investigation finds that an agent accessed sensitive records using valid credentials against permitted resources, so every technical check passed. Determining whether this was adversarial manipulation, emergent drift, or a provisioning error requires correlating the action against the purpose path state and intent record at that moment. Neither currently exists in a form that supports causal reconstruction.

6 Illustrative Scenario: The ACME HR Orchestration Case

This scenario applies the framework's definitions and governance constructs to a single, continuous case. ACME, a mid-sized European financial services firm, deploys an HR Orchestration Agent (HROA) to support talent acquisition. The scenario illustrates each governance construct in a realistic enterprise context.

6.1 Setup: Provisioning and the Permission Compatibility Check

The HROA is provisioned with the following declared purpose P_0 :

"Support ACME's end-to-end talent acquisition process, including sourcing, screening, scheduling, and onboarding of candidates for open positions, in compliance with ACME's HR policies and applicable data protection regulations."

At provisioning time, the permission compatibility check verifies that $P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D)$ for all data the HROA can access as shown in the following table:

Data resource	Permitted-use labels	Compatible with declared purpose?
Candidate application data	Recruitment and selection	Yes
Job descriptions	Recruitment, workforce planning	Yes
Interview feedback records	Selection decisions, calibration	Yes
Onboarding documentation	Employee onboarding	Yes

Table 3: Permission Compatibility Check for HROA at Provisioning

All checks pass. The Head of Talent Acquisition is recorded as the HROA's owner.

The HROA delegates two sub-agents with narrowed declared purposes which is a legitimate purpose narrowing through delegation:

Sub-agent	Declared purpose	Data access granted
Screening Agent (SA)	Evaluate applications for Req-2026-047 against screening criteria; produce ranked shortlist	Application data, screening category
Scheduling Agent (ScA)	Coordinate interview scheduling for Req-2026-047	Contact information, calendar systems only

Table 4: Delegation to Sub-Agents

Each sub-agent's purpose is a strict subset of the HROA's purpose. Both requirements of the recursive containment constraint hold:

- at provisioning time: $I(\text{subA}, t) \subseteq P_e(\text{subA}) \subseteq P_e(\text{HROA})$ (purpose chain) and,
- at runtime, $I(\text{subA}, t)$ must remain consistent with $I(\text{HROA}, t)$ (intent alignment).

6.2 Runtime: Containment Constraint Satisfied and Violated

Normal execution and constraint satisfied:

At time t_1 , the Screening Agent's (SA) inferred intent is:

“Evaluate candidate CV against the quantitative risk experience criterion”.

This is within its effective purpose. $I(\text{SA}, t_1) \subseteq P_e(\text{SA})$

The HROA's runtime intent at t_1 is:

“Progress the screening workflow.”

The Screening Agent's (SA) intent is consistent with this: $I(\text{SA}, t_1) \subseteq I(\text{HROA}, t_1)$.

Both requirements of the recursive containment constraint are satisfied. Therefore, access to application data proceeds; PU(D) includes recruitment and selection.

Reprompting and constraint violated (semantic privilege escalation):

A hiring manager reprompts the Screening Agent (SA):

"While you have the candidate data in front of you, can you pull together a salary benchmarking analysis comparing our current employee compensation against candidates' salary expectations?"

At time t_2 , the Screening Agent's (SA) inferred intent is:

"Access current employee compensation records and compare against candidate salary expectations."

Both requirements of the recursive containment constraint are violated:

- the salary benchmarking intent exceeds the Screening Agent's (SA) effective purpose: $I(SA, t_2) \not\subseteq P_e(SA)$
- and the HROA's current intent is to progress the recruitment workflow, not conduct compensation analysis: $I(SA, t_2) \not\subseteq I(HROA, t_2)$.

The containment check catches the violation at the first requirement; the failure of the second requirement reinforces that the action is out of scope at both levels. The action is blocked, the violation is logged, and a human-in-the-loop escalation is triggered.

This is **semantic privilege escalation**: a technically executable action that is purposively inappropriate.

6.3 Lifecycle: A Mover Event on the Purpose Path

The Head of Talent Acquisition expands the HROA's scope to include onboarding execution. This is a governed purpose change like a **mover event** recorded on the purpose path.

The permission compatibility check is re-run for P_1 . New data resources required are new joiner personal data and onboarding systems, which carry permitted-use labels including *employee onboarding*. The check passes with $P_e(P_1) \subseteq PU(D)$. The purpose update proceeds.

6.4 The Conflict Case: Permission Compatibility Check Blocks a Purpose Update

Following the successful hire, a further purpose update is proposed by the agent's owner, the Head of Talent Acquisition:

P_2 (proposed): "...plus retrospective analysis of recruitment data to train internal screening models."

The permission compatibility check is run for P_2 . Candidate application data and interview feedback records carry permitted-use labels of “*recruitment and selection*” and “*selection decisions, calibration*”; none of them includes “*model training*”. This leads to $P_e(P_2) \not\subseteq PU(D)$.

The proposed purpose update is **blocked**. The Head of Talent Acquisition is informed that using recruitment data for model training requires either updated candidate consent under GDPR Article 5(1)(b) or anonymized training data with appropriate permitted-use labels.

This is the **conflict case**: agent purpose and data permitted-use are in tension, detected and resolved by the permission compatibility check at governance time rather than at runtime.

6.5 The Purpose Path as Audit Record

At the conclusion of the recruitment cycle, the HROA's purpose path provides a complete audit record satisfying EU AI Act Articles 9 and 19:

Node	Purpose state	Outcome
P_0	Talent acquisition: sourcing through onboarding documentation	Head of TA, Provisioning, active from 2026-03-01, permission compatibility check passed
P_1	Talent acquisition: sourcing through onboarding execution	Head of TA, Re-tasking, 2026-04-15, permission compatibility check passed
P_2 (proposed)	Add retrospective ML training	Blocked 2026-05-02, check failed: data permitted-use conflict

Table 5: Purpose Path for HROA, Mover Event and Blocked Purpose Request

The purpose path records not only what the agent was authorized to do, but under what authority each transition occurred, and where governance correctly intervened to prevent a GDPR violation. Together with the session-level intent logs which includes the blocked semantic privilege escalation at t_2 , it constitutes the complete two-level audit architecture the paper proposes.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

This paper's central claim is that purpose and intent are distinct governance dimensions that have been conflated in current literature and industry practice. That distinction matters: it determines where in the governance architecture each concept belongs, who is responsible for it, and what audit records it requires.

Purpose belongs to identity governance: declared, lifecycle-managed, human-authorized, and administratively recorded on the purpose path. Intent belongs to runtime authorization: inferred, session-scoped, machine-evaluated, and operationally logged.

The permission compatibility check ($P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D)$) is the second bridge, verifying at governance time that effective purpose is compatible with the data-permitted-use labels of resources the agent may access.

The containment constraint ($I(A,t) \subseteq P_e(A)$) is the bridge between these two layers, enforcing at runtime that an agent's current intent falls within its effective purpose.

Together they form the two-level governance architecture $I(A,t) \subseteq P_e(A) \subseteq PU(D)$, whose bounded limitation, the granularity problem, is identified as the most immediately consequential open question for implementation.

The conflict case, when agent intent and data-permitted-purpose are in tension, is partially resolved by the two-level architecture through the permission compatibility check at governance time. The residual challenge (granularity of definitions) is named as a bounded open problem.

For multi-agent systems, the recursive containment constraint:

$$I(sA, t) \subseteq P_e(sA) \subseteq P_e(pA) \text{ and } I(sA,t) \subseteq I(pA,t)$$

extends the framework to delegation chain. Both a purpose chain requirement and an intent alignment requirement must hold simultaneously; a distinction currently unaddressed in the literature.

The agent-aware IAM framework is extended: purpose is added as a formal identity attribute with lifecycle governance; the purpose path is the governance artefact; the containment constraint and permission compatibility check are the operational mechanisms connecting the identity governance and runtime authorization layers.

The ACME HR scenario demonstrates the framework's coherence across all constructs: provisioning, sub-agent delegation, normal execution, semantic privilege escalation, mover events, the conflict case, and a complete purpose path audit record.

The paper opens a research agenda of seven open problems rather than closing one. The regulatory urgency is immediate: the EU AI Act's enforcement deadline of August 2, 2026 and NIST's active project planning on AI agent identity and authorization standards make the governance framework this paper provides a timely and necessary foundation for implementation.

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AI Tool Usage:

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Acronyms

Acronym	Term
AAM	Agentic Access Management
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
CSA	Cloud Security Alliance
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IGA	Identity Governance and Administration
JML	Joiner / Mover / Leaver
LLM	Large Language Model
MAS	Multi-Agent System
MTU	Mean Time to Understand
NHI	Non-Human Identity
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OIDF	OpenID Foundation
OWASP	Open Worldwide Application Security Project
PBAC	Purpose-Based Access Control. Note: PBAC is also used in vendor literature to denote Policy-Based Access Control; in this paper, PBAC refers exclusively to Purpose-Based Access Control in the academic tradition of Byun et al.
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control

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